

EVALUATION OF OPERATIVE SURGICAL SAFETY AND NURSING COMPLIANCE AT MOSUL TEACHING HOSPITALS

Omer Akram Muhsin

Nineveh health director / Al – Salam teaching hospital

Prof. Hanady Jabbar Mahmood

University of Mosul / Nursing college

Abstract: Background: Surgery is the discipline of medicine concerned with the surgical manipulation of a bodily structure in order to detect, avoid, or cure a disease. Ambroise Paré, a sixteenth-century French physician, claimed that performing operation is, "To eliminate that which is superfluous, restore that which has been dislocated, separate that which has been united, join that which has been divided and repair the defects of nature."

Aim: To evaluate surgical safety and nursing compliance at Mosul teaching hospitals and to assess using (WHO) surgical safety checklist at Mosul teaching hospitals

Methods: The study uses a descriptive study design to achieve the study's aims over the period from the 5th October 2021 until the 6th December 2022. The study is comprised of 104 OT nurses included in this study.

Results shows that most of the study participants were male with an age mean of 36.7 years old, 8.5 years of experience in OT, they have a bachelor's degree, from urban residency, and working in Al-Jumhory teaching hospital of Mosul city and the overall mean of "SIGN-IN": Upon arrival of the patient in the OR theater, before induction of anesthesia was 10.11, "TIME OUT": Before skin incision was 8.43, and "SIGN-OUT": Before patient leaves the operating room was 7.23.

Conclusions: The research suggests that not every patient treated to a (WHO) operational safety checklist enjoy better postoperative outcomes, but this could simply reflect the overall quality of care in institutions where checklist use is widespread.

Key words: Operating Safety, Nursing Compliance, Operation.

1.1 Introduction

Ensuring patient safety within the surgical environment starts even before the patient enters the operating suite and encompasses monitoring for all forms of preventable medical errors, including medication-related mistakes. However, surgical errors specifically pertain to this setting. Recommended preventive measures against errors such as performing surgery on the wrong site, incorrect patient, incorrect procedure, or leaving foreign objects inside patients include initiating clear, structured communication among the patient, surgeon(s), and other healthcare professionals involved in patient care. All workers involved in the patient's care must be aware of the need to prevent surgical errors (Fathy et al.).

The World Health Organization (WHO) has undertaken several International and regional initiatives have been developed to enhance surgical safety, largely inspired by the World Health Organization's Second Global Patient Safety Challenge titled "Safe Surgery Saves Lives." This initiative seeks to elevate the safety standards of surgical care worldwide by establishing a fundamental set of safety guidelines suitable for adoption by all WHO member states (Russ et al., 2015).

Possible avoidable surgical mistakes have attracted more attention in recent years, despite the fact that they appear to be less common than other kinds of medical errors. Since 1995, the Joint Commission has been collecting data on reported sentinel events, and wrong-site surgery has consistently been the most frequently cited reason (Bratch & Pandit, 2021).

In the latest year with available data, an analysis was conducted on 117 sentinel incidents involving wrong-site surgeries. While the Joint Commission's website does not provide specialty-specific statistics, it emphasizes that no surgical specialty is completely exempt from the risk of surgical errors. (Clapper & Ching, 2020).

2. method

The process of research and data collection methods, as well as the data analysis, are explained in detail.

2.1 administrative Issues:

The Nursing College at the University of Mosul and the Nineveh Health Directorate's Ethical Research Committee provided formal approval for the study's conduct. The researcher obtained an agreement from hospital administrators at Mosul teaching hospitals.

2.2 Design:

The current study adopts a descriptive study design to accomplish the objectives of the study for the period from the 5th October 2021 until the 6st December 2022. The study is comprised of 104 OT nurses included in this study.

2.3 Study Setting:

The study has been carried out in three teaching hospitals in Mosul city, which is located in the north region of Iraq. The hospitals were (AL-Salam, AL- Jumhuri and Ibn-Sina teaching hospitals).

Statistical Package did statistical data analysis for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. A descriptive approach is applied. Mean (range) or frequency and chi-square (percentage) are computed.

3 Results

Table (3.1): demographical characteristic of study subjects

Category	mean	SD
Age	36.7	5.47
Years Of Experience In OT	8.5	3.7
Gender	Freq.	%
Male	70	66.7
Female	35	33.3
Educational Level		
Diploma	33	31.4
Bachelors	72	68.6
Residency		
Rural	47	44.8

Urban	58	55.2
Type of Surgery		
Minor	26	24.8
Major	52	49.5
Super Major	27	25.7
Name of hospital		
Al Salam	40	38.1
Ibn sina	27	25.7
Al Jumhory	38	36.2

Table (4.1) shows that most of the study participants were male with an age mean of 36.7 years old, 8.5 years of experience in OT, they have a bachelor's degree, from urban residency, and working in Al-Jumhory teaching hospital of Mosul city.

Table (3.2) Surgical Safety Checklist utilization among operated surgical patients

Category	N	Range	minimum	maximum	mean	Std
SIGN-IN: Upon arrival of the patient in the OR theater, before induction of anesthesia	105	11	3	14	10.11	2.54
TIME OUT: Before skin incision	105	17	0	17	8.43	2.8
SIGN-OUT: Before patient leaves the operating room	105	15	0	15	7.23	3.2

This table shows utilization was highest during the first phase (mean=10.11/14), moderate during TIME OUT (mean=8.43/17), and lowest at last (mean=7.23/15), reflecting a decreasing trend in list adherence as surgery progressed.

Table (3.3) Surgical Safety Checklist utilization among operated surgical patients according to nurses' gender

Surgical Safety Checklist		N	MEAN	std	T value
SIGN-IN: Upon arrival of the patient in the OR theater, before induction of anesthesia	Male	70	10.028	2.472	0.49
	Female	35	10.294	2.725	
TIME OUT: Before skin incision	Male	70	8.521	2.980	0.43
	Female	35	8.264	2.415	
SIGN-IN: Upon arrival of the patient in the OR theater, before induction of anesthesia	Male	70	7.211	3.193	0.12
	female	35	7.294	3.261	

The table indicates a statistically significant difference between male and female patients regarding the "TIME OUT": Before skin incision" variable, with a P-value greater than 0.05.

Table (3.4) Surgical Safety Checklist utilization among operated surgical patients according to nurses' age

Category		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
SIGN-IN: Upon arrival of the patient in the OR theater, before induction of anesthesia TIME OUT: Before skin incision	Between Groups	68.903	2	34.451	5.801	.004
	Within Groups	605.726	102	5.938		
	Total	674.629	104			
SIGN-IN: Upon arrival of the patient in the OR theater, before induction of anesthesia TIME OUT: Before skin incision	Between Groups	59.060	2	29.530	3.980	.022
	Within Groups	756.787	102	7.419		
	Total	815.848	104			
SIGN-IN: Upon arrival of the patient in the OR theater, before induction of anesthesia	Between Groups	82.428	2	41.214	4.278	.016
	Within Groups	982.620	102	9.634		
	Total	1065.048	104			

This table shows a significance statistically difference according to the age group between study groups in: Upon arrival of the patient in the OR theater, before induction of anesthesia: Before skin incision,,: Upon arrival of the patient in the OR theater, before induction of anesthesia: Before skin incision, and: Before skin incision at P-value < 0.05.

5. Discussion

Table (1) from the current study shows that the majority of participants were males, the mean age was 36.7 years old, they had 8.5 years of experience in OT, 68.6% had a bachelor's degree and 31.4% had a diploma degree, 55.2% were urban residents, and 38.1% worked in Al-Slam, 36.2% worked in Al-Jumhory, and 25.7% worked in Ibn-sina teaching hospital in Mosul. Major operations were found to have a rate of 49.5%, Super Major operations at a rate of 25.7%, and Minor operations at a rate of 24.8% across all three hospitals (Al-Salam, Al-Jumhory, and Ibn Sina). Consistent with these results, Robert (2018) observed that the severity of clinical BPH increases with age and that up to 30% of men over the age of 65 experience LUTS.

A total of 450 clinicians from 2 universities in Northwest Ethiopia were surveyed for the "research Occupational Stress among Operation Room Clinicians at Ethiopian University Hospitals," with data from 388 (or 86.2%) of them being used in the study's final analysis. Three hundred and six (78.1%) of the doctors were males, and 202 (52.0%) of them were single. Individuals' ages range from 23 to 51, with 29 (27-32) being the median (interquartile range) of the data set. A majority (201, or 51.8%) of responders were young adults (aged 25-29). There were 249 (64.2%) first-degree holders and 351 (90.5%) clinicians with less than or equal to 5 years of experience in the operating room. Sixty-six percent, or 260, of the clinicians said they worked regular shifts (Slaatto et al., 2022). Patients who had been married for 31–40 years had a significantly higher frequency of BPH than those who had been married for fewer years. Findings on educational attainment are consistent with a 2019 study by Ann-Catrin Blomberg, which found that 26.2% of college graduates were in the bachelor's degree bracket (Blomberg et al., 2019).

When compared to IhnsookJeong in South Korea, where just 24% of OT nurses had advanced degrees, the percentage in the former case, at 76%, is striking (Jeong et al., 2008). Even though the hospital claimed 100% checklist usage in the OR, our observational analysis observed only 40% compliance with a wide range of completeness of items (63.4%). After 3 years of what seems to have been a basic introduction without extensive reinforcement training, 40% instrument usage is fairly good. The sign-in process took on average & Sd (10.11, 2.54) of time, with the biggest percentage of time spent checking anesthetic equipment and medications. In most instances, a working pulse oximeter was also attached, which aided in the early detection of desaturation. However, most instances lacked checks for aspiration risk, anticipated difficult airway, allergy history, and predicted blood loss; all four of these factors have been linked to fatalities (Kasatpibal et al., 2012).

The World Health Organization's Surgical Safety Checklist aims to improve communication between surgical teams (Lingard et al., 2005). During the time-out, surgical teams should formally identify themselves to one another and describe their respective roles on the team. Despite this, the data from this study showed that only 56.3% of team members identified themselves by name and role on average and with standard deviation (2.8, 8.43). This finding is consistent with a similar study done in Thailand, which found that the vast majority of surgical staff members failed to properly identify themselves and their roles to their coworkers (Lingard et al., 2004).

Possible explanations include extended periods of communication and introductions between surgical teams in the operating room. What's more, first contact is generally the only time people identify themselves. Numerous studies have shown the dangers of poor team communication and collaboration during surgery (Mishra et al., 2008).

The results showed that the sign-out process was the least efficient overall (54.3%), with a mean and Sd of (7.23, 7.23). Hospital data from the UK and Thailand confirm this (Conley et al., 2011) (Conley et al., 2011; Lingard et al., 2004)

It's possible that the occupied surgical teams (nursing staff with final instrument count, processing, and preparation for the next case; surgical and anesthesia staff with patient extubating, oxygen preparation in the recovery room, procedure note writing, and patient transfer) were to blame for the delay.

Most medical mistakes can be traced back to poor communication. The proper person doesn't get the message, the message is misinterpreted, or problems aren't addressed until they've reached a crisis point. In the operating room, this results in blunders, ineffective use of materials, wasted tools, agitation, low morale, and delays (Carli et al., 2021)

5. Conclusions

The surgical safety checklist is a simple method, and there is evidence for its effectiveness in reducing complications in clinical use. WHO recommends using the checklist in all surgical operations and encourages clinicians to modify the list for different specialties and hospitals. Isn't all Patients exposed to a surgical safety checklist experience better postoperative outcomes, but this could simply reflect wider quality of care in hospitals where checklist use is routine.

References:

1. Bratch, R., & Pandit, J. J. (2021). An integrative review of method types used in the study of medication error during anaesthesia: implications for estimating incidence. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 127(3), 458-469.
2. Brown, B., Bermingham, S., Vermeulen, M., Jennings, B., Adamek, K., Markou, M., Bassham, J. E., & Hibbert, P. (2021). Surgical safety checklist audits may be misleading! Improving the implementation

- and adherence of the surgical safety checklist: a quality improvement project. *BMJ open quality*, 10(4), e001593.
3. Carli, F., Awasthi, R., Gillis, C., Baldini, G., Bessissow, A., Liberman, A. S., & Minnella, E. M. (2021). Integrating prehabilitation in the preoperative clinic: a paradigm shift in perioperative care. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, 132(5), 1494-1500
 4. Clapper, T. C., & Ching, K. (2020). Debunking the myth that the majority of medical errors are attributed to communication. *Medical Education*, 54(1), 74-81.
 5. Conley, D. M., Singer, S. J., Edmondson, L., Berry, W. R., & Gawande, A. A. (2011). Effective surgical safety checklist implementation. *Journal of the American College of Surgeons*, 212(5), 873-879.
 6. Dobson, G. P. (2020). Trauma of major surgery: a global problem that is not going away. In (Vol. 81, pp. 47-54): Elsevier.
 7. Fathy, E. A., Abdalla, K. F., Abdelatif, D. A., & Dessowky, S. M. Nurses' Performance Regarding the Patients' Safety Measures in Operating Theater.
 8. Gillespie, B. M., Harbeck, E. L., Lavin, J., Hamilton, K., Gardiner, T., Withers, T. K., & Marshall, A. P. (2018). Evaluation of a patient safety programme on Surgical Safety Checklist Compliance: a prospective longitudinal study. *BMJ open quality*, 7(3), e000362.
 9. Jeong, I., Cho, J., & Park, S. (2008). Compliance with standard precautions among operating room nurses in South Korea. *American journal of infection control*, 36(10), 739-742.
 10. Kasatpibal, N., Senaratana, W., Chitreecheur, J., Chotirosniramit, N., Pakvipas, P., & Junthasopeepun, P. (2012). Implementation of the World Health Organization surgical safety checklist at a university hospital in Thailand. *Surgical infections*, 13(1), 50-56
 11. Lingard, L., Espin, S., Rubin, B., Whyte, S., Colmenares, M., Baker, G. R., Doran, D., Grober, E., Orser, B., & Bohnen, J. (2005). Getting teams to talk: development and pilot implementation of a checklist to promote interprofessional communication in the OR. *BMJ Quality & Safety*, 14(5), 340-346.
 12. Lingard, L., Espin, S., Whyte, S., Regehr, G., Baker, G. R., Reznick, R., Bohnen, J., Orser, B., Doran, D., & Grober, E. (2004). Communication failures in the operating room: an observational classification of recurrent types and effects. *BMJ Quality & Safety*, 13(5), 330-334
 13. Mahmood, T., Mylopoulos, M., Bagli, D., Damignani, R., & Haji, F. A. (2019). A mixed methods study of challenges in the implementation and use of the surgical safety checklist. *Surgery*, 165(4), 832-837.
 14. Russ, S. J., Sevdalis, N., Moorthy, K., Mayer, E. K., Rout, S., Caris, J., Mansell, J., Davies, R., Vincent, C., & Darzi, A. (2015). A qualitative evaluation of the barriers and facilitators toward implementation of the WHO surgical safety checklist across hospitals in England: lessons from the "Surgical Checklist Implementation Project". *Annals of surgery*, 261(1), 81-91.
 15. Slaatto, A., Mellblom, A. V., Kleppe, L. C., & Baugerud, G. A. (2022). Safety in Residential Youth Facilities: Staff Perceptions of Safety and Experiences of the "Basic Training Program in Safety and 114 Security". *Residential Treatment for Children & Youth*, 39(2), 212- 237.